

METHODOLOGY, THEORY AND METHODS OF TEACHING HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATSIA

In this article, the methodology of historical science, its content, historical theory and methods are discussed. In innovation methods, scientific processes, the general public knowledge of science and technology thoughts Methodological points are discussed.

Keywords: Methodology, theory, function, method, knowledge, modeling, hypothesis, hypothesis, concept, empirical semantic;

INTRODUCTION

The methodology of historical science is an activity of scientific knowledge, an activity aimed at the implementation, analysis and study of historical research. Methodology determines the nature of setting scientific problems, determines the most optimal principles and directions for their solution, research methods critical evaluates and analysis does.

As every science has its importance, the history of Uzbekistan has its own methodological scientific and theoretical bases and principles. These constitute the basis of the science of history of Uzbekistan and are of great importance for its development, increasing influence in the interest of society and the people. Scientific-theoretical principles serve the truthful writing of the history of the Motherland, the emergence of historical truth. If history is a social necessity and spiritual-educational need for human existence and development, then the science of history is a high intellectual, scientific-practical activity responsible for the realization of these needs. The effectiveness of this, that is, the principles of methodological scientific ideas and theories in the development of the science of history, directly help to reveal the content and essence and philosophy of history in depth, as well as the full realization of the goals and tasks of the science of history. It is a very important issue what the methodological scientific-theoretical foundations, ideas and teachings of the history of Uzbekistan consist of.

First, history is the science of social development. Its subject is a science that studies the past of human society, the development and change process in various fields. Secondly, history is the science of humanity, which determines the past of society through research, researching the processes created by man in the past, which are the results of his intelligence, and the period before us. It is a science that can be learned and passed on to the next generation.

Style (methods) using historian or researcher new knowledge change or historical processes about current views determine and the same at the time to them precision input

possible This views are history science methodology concept if the initial views about methodology of science in the field of modern history concept historical to know theoretical fully explaining its foundations, showing its problematic aspects of a theoretical nature to give is used as

History of science scientific and social position, of history science learns the quality structure. Creates a theory of historical knowledge (including general philosophical, gnesological and epistemological foundations, principles, levels, types, stages, methods of historical knowledge, manifestation of the results of historical knowledge, as well as forms of historical knowledge) . also history science methodology history in science main theoretical and methodological directions, different scientific schools and their characteristics learns

History philosophy concept history science methodology component as understood. New period "history philosophy" the term also appeared , this expression first appeared in 1765, the historian just historical events descriptive only without remaining perhaps historical the process French Enlightenment who believed that he should try to understand philosophically Voltaire (1694-1778) by applied.

History science methodology independent science as XIX century was formed during the last quarter - the beginning of the 20th century. During this period, the methodological problems of the science of history began to be studied more intensively in Germany than elsewhere , and two distinctive "schools" in this regard formed. Baden of the school leader representatives german historian and philosophers V. Windelband (1848-1915) and G. Rickert (1863-1936) s was They are yourselves of science methodology regarding formed their views and expressed it as follows: - "the task of natural sciences is general laws forms history of science task - separately is to describe the evidence".

processes leading to a specific goal in the process of method-historical research , the method itself from theory, research methodology and from the technique content finds

Any method is theoretically based , and at the same time objective and subjective feature of the profession has an objective basis. However giving special importance to it must each how the method is also objective to conclusions take not coming possible In this selection of the method, its correct application and drawing of critical conclusions taken of the researcher directly to himself depends and it acquires its main importance .

Methodology to know philosophical theory, sociology and based on historiography is formed. naturally to know theory issues this in science the main place holds however this with main attention that's it focus possible rather than theoretical knowledge historical studies practice to be perfected with must Such historical studies philosophers by done not increased therefore for their history science methodology regarding stated thoughts a lot cases debate and to the discussion reason will be mostly cases and a historian - practitioners their thoughts directly denial they do.

Theory of historical knowledge while studying the methodology of historical science course about different thoughts is studied their historical to knowledge is typical priority directions main attention is focused. Philosophical knowledge of historians and philosophical approaches to research essence too deep possessions important important at the same time of philosophers too historical practical research importance deep they know is important. That's it without each two representatives of science fields to achieve perfection of theoretical knowledge possible This while historical of research theoretical of importance leads to an increase.

On the methodology of history science in the years after the Second World War debate and discussions again the climax took New theoretical and philosophical views forming

social and humanitarian in the sciences interdisciplinary the approach was decided. A pre-existing dispute - that history is a science (scientists) or that it is a form of art and literature (anti-scientists) regarding the most big scientists with participation arguments again escalated.

In this of the historian personal views and social belonging to e shows that it should not be ignored. Although some to mistakes if uo'1 is put, objective interpretation is important. This period discussion and one of the concepts that fueled the debate was an interdisciplinary approach .

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that the scientific research conducted for the study of history must be based on theoretical methods, because the researcher's research is based on a certain scientific and theoretical basis. will have and research will be conducted based on this process. For this reason, a researcher or a teacher of history who is conducting research in history must first of all know the theories and methods that exist in history and are recognized in world history. This ensures that the researcher has a high level of scientific and theoretical knowledge. In this article, we have presented several points that justify the role and importance of theory in the science of history.

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